

Evaluating repeatability and reproducibility of in-vivo imaging using a portable Halbach-based 47mT scanner

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Abstract

Purpose: Low-field (LF) MRI scanners are emerging as a portable, cost-effective point-of-care solution. Their minimal infrastructure enables deployment in hospitals, remote areas, and mobile units. However, these advantages introduce unique challenges, as environmental variability may impact scanner stability. This underscores the need to evaluate the robustness of LF MRI systems.

Methods: We evaluated the repeatability and reproducibility of signal-to-noise ratio (SNR), contrast-to-noise ratio (CNR), and post-segmentation tissue volume in white matter (WM), grey matter (GM) and cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) in five healthy volunteers across five scan sessions. These included three sessions performed on different days in our standard scanning location, one in the intensive care unit, and one in a van, using our in-house 47 mT Halbach-based MRI scanner. Each session included a proton-density weighted scan (PDw), a T2 weighted scan (T2w), and a short inversion recovery T1 weighted scan (IR-T1w).

Results: PDw scans yielded the highest SNR but the lowest WM-GM CNR, whereas T2w and IR-T1w scans showed lower SNR but higher GM-WM CNR. Intra-subject repeatability and reproducibility were strong, with only minor variations in specific metrics, such as a slight increase in noise level in PDw scan in the van. WM, GM, and CSF volumes were consistent across modalities, locations, and aligned with prior reports.

Conclusion: The performance of the LF system is repeatable across time points and reproducible in different locations. Although larger clinical studies are needed, our findings establish a benchmark and emphasize the need for a rigorous evaluation of portable LF MRI.

1. Introduction

Low-field (LF) MRI scanners ($B_0 < 0.1\text{T}$) are emerging as accessible, patient-friendly imaging systems with promising applications(1-3). LF MRI systems are often mobile and compact, requiring minimal space and infrastructure for installation and operation. The lack of strict siting requirements – such as the need for a Faraday cage or extensive shielding – simplifies installation and further enhances their accessibility. These advantages make them well-suited for point-of-care (POC) use in hospitals(4), where bedside imaging can aid in clinical decision-making and reduces risks associated with transport of patients to conventional high-field scanners. Additionally, their mobility enables deployment in remote(5) or resource-limited areas, as well as in ambulances and mobile units(6), expanding access to MRI beyond traditional clinical settings. Recent studies have shown the potential of LF MRI for POC neuroimaging(7), particularly in the assessment of stroke(3, 8, 9). While development has primarily focused on neuroimaging, recent advancements have demonstrated the feasibility of extremity(2, 10-12) and whole-body imaging(1). Beyond the considerable financial advantages, LF MRI has reduced contraindications(13), enabling patients with metallic implants - who are usually ineligible for high-field (HF) MRI – to be scanned safely(14, 15).

Reproducibility in medical imaging refers to the ability to obtain consistent and reliable measurements across repeated scans, different operators, and various imaging systems. In MRI, ensuring reproducibility is essential for clinical applications, as it directly impacts diagnostic confidence and treatment planning(16). For example, in longitudinal patient monitoring, where changes in tissue characteristics over time are assessed, a lack of reproducibility can lead to misinterpretations of disease progression or treatment response. In research settings, reproducibility is critical for validating findings, comparing results across studies, and establishing standardized imaging biomarkers(17). Despite its importance, reproducibility in LF MRI(18)—has so far received very little attention from the scientific community. LF systems are still in an early stage of development, with few systematic studies assessing their reproducibility across different sessions, protocols, and patient populations(19, 20).

At LF, achieving reproducibility presents unique challenges compared to HF systems. One key factor is the inherently lower signal-to-noise ratio (SNR)(21), which affects measurement precision. (22) Operating in less controlled new environments, such as fluctuating temperature, humidity, and potential electromagnetic interference (EMI), introduces factors that may impact the overall system stability and consequently, the image quality(19). This underscores the need for studies to focus on the performance and reliability of LF MRI systems for in-vivo scanning across diverse settings, providing critical insights into their real-world applicability. Although rare, recent work has begun to address this gap: a study investigated the

reproducible performance of a 72mT portable LF MRI scanner for knee imaging in one subject in five distinct locations. Despite differences in EMI between sites, the authors showed that scan images preserved the main anatomical information(10).

In this study, we evaluated the reproducibility of signal-to-noise ratio (SNR), contrast-to-noise ratio (CNR), and post-segmentation tissue volume/fraction in white matter (WM), gray matter (GM), and cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) in five healthy volunteers. Each volunteer underwent five scan sessions using our in-house 47mT Halbach-based MRI scanner: three scans were performed on different days at (i) our standard scanning location (the lab), and two additional scans were conducted in non-standard locations, specifically (ii) the intensive care unit (ICU) and (iii) in a van. The ICU was chosen as it represents one of the most likely clinical environments where LF MRI could be deployed, given the need for bedside imaging in critically ill patients. The van was selected to simulate imaging in a transportable setting, such as a truck or an ambulance, which could be used to bring MRI to remote or underserved areas. By including these different locations, we aimed to assess not only intra-subject repeatability and reproducibility but also the potential impact of environmental factors on image robustness.

2. Materials and Methods

Hardware

All data were acquired on an in-house developed 47mT Halbach-based MRI scanner equipped with a Barthel RF amplifier (Aachen, Germany), AE Techron 7224/2105 gradient amplifiers (Elkhart, USA), and a Magritek Kea2 spectrometer (Aachen, Germany), shown in *Figure 1A*. All acquisitions were performed using an elliptical spiral-solenoid transmit-receive head coil (18cm width, 24cm height, 16cm long with 15 turns of 1.5mm diameter litz wire), with $Q_{\text{loaded/unloaded}} = 220/160$ (2, 23). Details of the magnet design have been published previously(23). The scanner has a bore of 30cm, length 50 cm, width 60 cm, weighs approximately 150kg, and can be wheeled to various locations manually by a single operator. The B_0 homogeneity of the scanner was optimised using a two-stage optimization scheme. First, the scanner was designed using a genetic algorithm which maximizes the magnetic field homogeneity in part-per-million (ppm) over a 25cm diameter spherical volume at the center of the magnet. Details of the optimization have been described previously(24), and the source code are available at <https://github.com/LUMC-LowFieldMRI/HalbachOptimisation>. Secondly, the magnet was built and mapped over a 25cm diameter spherical volume (DSV) with a Teslameter attached to a 3D positioning robot (<https://gitlab.com/osii/tools/cosi-measure>). The acquired field maps were fitted to up to 20th order spherical harmonics to reduce noise. Shim magnets (up to 6mm) were then placed in 12 holders located on

the outside of the magnet, with each holder able to accommodate 49 magnet trays. The final homogeneity maps are shown in *Figure 1B-C*.

Figure 1. **A.** Schematic of the 47 mT Halbach-array MRI scanner used in this study. **B.** Map of the magnetic-field homogeneity, expressed in mT, across a three-dimensional 25cm spherical volume. **C.** Central axial, coronal, and sagittal imaging planes.

Participants

Five healthy volunteers (age 24-61yo, 4F/1M) participated in this study. The study adhered to the guidelines of the Leiden University Medical Center Institutional Review Board (The Netherlands). Written informed consent was obtained from all subjects prior to the study. Each participant underwent five scan sessions: (i) three sessions (on different days) in our usual scan location [lab, *Figure 2A*], (ii) one session at the intensive care unit [ICU, *Figure 2A*], and (iii) one session in a van [*Figure 2A*].

Figure 2. A. Locations in which the subjects were imaged: in the lab (standard conditions), in the intensive care unit, and in a van; B. Example of scan images obtained from a subject in two areas of the brain, with the 3 MR sequences used in this study, consisting of PD-weighted, T₂-weighted, and short Inversion Time (TI) scans.

MRI protocol

For each scan session, three MR sequences were acquired: (1) PD-weighted (PDw), T₂-weighted (T2w), and an inversion-recovery (IR) T₁-weighted (IR-T1w) scans (see *Figure 2B*). All scans used a 3D turbo spin echo (TSE) sequence and the following scan parameters: field-of-view (FOV, Anterior-Posterior [AP], Right-Left [RL], Front-Head [FH]) = 225x205x190mm³, resolution (AP, RL, FH) = 1.5x1.5x5mm³, imaging acquisition bandwidth (BW) = 20kHz, k-space circular-windowing. The PDw protocol used echo time (TE)/repetition time (TR) = 16/600ms, a center-out k-space trajectory, and an echo train length (ETL) = 8. The T₂w protocol used TE/TR = 150/2500ms, a linear k-space trajectory, and an echo train length (ETL) = 15. The IR-T₁w protocol used echo time TE/TR = 20/1200ms, an inversion time (TI) = 91ms, a center-out k-space trajectory, and an echo train length (ETL) = 8.

Processing

All data were processed in Python 3.9. First, an intensity correction for the coil high Q was estimated using frequency-dependent noise profiles and applied to the raw k-space data, as described previously(23). Then, images were reconstructed using a standard fast Fourier transform (FFT) and normalized for intensity by its maximum intensity value. The reconstructed images were automatically segmented into white matter (WM), gray matter (GM), and cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) masks using SynthSeg(25), and resampled to 1×1×1 mm³ resolution.

SNR was calculated in WM, GM, and CSF by taking the average signal over five consecutive slices within the segmented masks and dividing by the noise level defined as the average of the standard deviation of the signal in four regions of interest (ROIs) placed in the image corners (Figure 3). CNR was calculated between WM and GM, WM and CSF, GM and CSF, and tissue (WM+GM) and CSF. The difference between the mean signal intensities (ΔS) was measured in five slices and divided by the noise standard deviation. These measurements were performed in two regions of the brain: (i) near the vertex of the head (area 1) and (ii) at the level of the ventricles (area 2, see Figure 3). Finally, the coefficient of variation (CoV) for each sequence was calculated as the ratio between the standard deviation and the mean of the SNR and CNR across the repeated measurements.

Finally, the volume of WM, GM, tissue (WM+GM), and CSF was computed by multiplying the number of voxels in each segmentation mask by the voxel size.

Reproducibility and repeatability analyses

Repeatability was assessed by comparing signal metrics in WM, GM, and CSF, along noise metrics, across the three laboratory sessions, treating subjects as a repeated factor.

To evaluate inter-location reproducibility, laboratory measurements were first averaged across the three sessions for each subject to yield a single representative estimate per participant and subsequently compared with measurements from the ICU and van.

Statistical analysis

Statistical significance for signal and noise metrics was evaluated using Friedman tests, accounting for the repeated-measures design and the non-normal distribution associated with the small sample size. Analyses were performed separately for each MR sequence.

All statistical tests were two-sided with a significance level of $\alpha = 0.05$. Given the limited number of subjects ($n = 5$), post-hoc Wilcoxon signed-rank tests were not formally interpreted, as the minimum attainable p-values under multiple-comparison correction exceed conventional significance thresholds ($p > 0.0625$).

Figure 3. Example segmentation masks of white matter (WM), gray matter (GM), tissue (WM+GM), and cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) generated by SynthSeg (25), shown alongside the defined noise ROIs. Results are presented for two brain regions: (i) at the level of the ventricles and (ii) near the vertex. Noise was estimated as the standard deviation of the signal within the four noise ROIs.

3. Results

Qualitative assessment of image quality across scanning environments

Figure 4 provides an overview of the PDw, T2w, and IR-T1w images from a representative participant across all five scanning sessions: three in the laboratory, one in the ICU, and one in a van. Overall, the images acquired from all locations and sessions exhibit clear depiction of major brain structures (e.g. cerebral cortex, ventricles, thalamus, caudate nucleus). Specifically, the PDw images show high signal intensity in WM and GM, allowing for clear differentiation between tissue and CSF. The T2w images exhibit, as expected, high signal intensity in CSF and lower WM/GM signal intensity. The IR-T1w images, designed to enhance contrast between WM and GM, present a well-defined contrast across all scanning environments.

The entire set of IR-T1w images is shown in Figure 5. For all volunteers, a consistent and clear differentiation between WM and GM is evident, including well-defined visualization of subcortical structures such as the caudate nucleus and thalamus. Corresponding PDw and T2w images are shown in the supplementary materials (Figure S1).

Figure 4. Scan images from a single volunteer (Volunteer 5), showing three different contrasts (PDw, T2w, and IR-T1w) acquired across five distinct scan sessions (Lab Sessions 1-3, ICU Session 1, Van Session 1). All images are from the same axial slice at the level of the ventricles. Note that images were co-registered (only for display) using SPM (Wellcome Institute of Neurology University College London, UK, <http://www.fil.ion.ucl.ac.uk/spm/doc/>) in Matlab (The MathWorks, Inc., Natick, Massachusetts, United States) to a common anatomical space to show corresponding brain slices for direct comparison.

Figure 5. Scan images from all volunteers, showing one contrast (IR-T1w) acquired across five distinct scan sessions (Lab Sessions 1-3, ICU Session 1, Van Session 1). All images are from the same axial slice at the level of the ventricles.

Quantitative assessment of image metrics across MRI sequences

As illustrated in Figure 6, PDw images yield the highest SNR for both WM and GM. However, the SNR levels for these two tissue types are remarkably similar; this lack of signal differentiation reflects the low tissue contrast qualitatively observed in Figure 4. Moreover, a slightly higher intra-subject variability is observed for PDw images (CoV~17%) compared to T2w and IR-T1w (CoV~10%, Table 1).

CNR analyses clearly illustrate that IR-T1w images provide the highest differentiation between WM and GM, while PDw and T2w scans yield the highest CNR for all contrasts involving CSF (Figure 7). Regarding measurement reliability, T2w results showed the lowest intra-subject variability (CoV ~8–11%). In contrast, the CoV of CNR for IR-T1w WM/CSF and PDw WM/GM reached the highest levels (73% and 58%, respectively; Table 1). These high values are a mathematical consequence of the near-isointensity between those specific tissue types in those sequences; when the mean difference between signals is near zero, contrast metrics become extremely sensitive to minor signal fluctuations/noise, rendering the CoV not particularly informative.

Quantitative results in Area 2 (ventricle level) followed a similar trend to Area 1 across all sequences, although absolute CoV values were generally higher (Table 1 and Figure S2-S3). This region-dependent increase in variability likely reflects the greater anatomical complexity and increased partial volume effects at the ventricle level, which may reduce the consistency of automated tissue segmentation compared to the more homogeneous regions at the top of the head.

Figure 6. Signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) measured from PDw, T2w and IR-T1w sequences, in white matter (WM), gray matter (GM), and cerebrospinal fluid (CSF), segmented by Synthseg, in Area 1 (the top of the head). Each data point represents the mean SNR from 5 slices, with different markers indicating the scan location. The boxplots summarize these data points for all locations, while colors differentiate individual subjects.

Figure 7. Contrast-to-noise ratio (CNR) from PDw, T2w and IR-T1w sequences, between different tissue types, as segmented by Synthseg, in Area 1 (the top of the head). The tissue types are white matter (“WM”), gray matter (“GM”),

cerebrospinal fluid (“CSF”) and white and gray matter together (“Tissue”). The boxplots summarize these data points for all locations, while colors differentiate individual subjects.

Area 1	CoV of CNR				CoV of SNR		
	WM/GM	WM/CSF	Tissue/CSF	GM/CSF	WM	GM	CSF
PDw	47%	19%	18%	17%	16%	15%	14%
T2w	8%	8%	9%	11%	11%	9%	9%
IR-T1w	8%	73%	37%	14%	10%	8%	9%

Area 2	CoV of CNR				CoV of SNR		
	WM/GM	WM/CSF	Tissue/CSF	GM/CSF	WM	GM	CSF
PDw	58%	24%	22%	22%	19%	18%	17%
T2w	13%	13%	14%	17%	11%	9%	12%
IR-T1w	12%	34%	47%	16%	9%	8%	9%

Table 1. Coefficient of variation (CoV) for signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) and contrast-to-noise ratio (CNR) for two brain areas: the top of the head (Area 1) and the ventricle level (Area 2). Each percentage value represents the CoV calculated from the average SNR or CNR per subject and location.

Repeatability and reproducibility of noise, signal levels, and tissue volumes

In Area 1, no significant differences in noise or WM/GM/CSF signal levels were observed for all three sequences in three lab scans acquired on different days (p-value 0.16, Figure 8, top row). When comparing results across scan locations (Figure 8, bottom row), most metrics remain unchanged, except for a significant increase in noise level observed between the lab and the van for the PDw scans (p-value 0.015) and in the CSF signal for the T2w scans (p-value 0.015). Results in Areas 1 and 2 are consistent (see Figure S4).

Volumetric measurements of total brain tissue (WM + GM), as well as individual WM, GM, and CSF volumes, remained consistent across all conditions (Figure 9). Statistical analysis revealed no significant differences either across the three repeated laboratory sessions or across the various scanning locations for any of the MRI sequences (p-value > 0.05).

Figure 8. Noise and signals in different tissue types measured from PDw (green), T2w (orange) and IR-T1w (blue) sequences in Area 1. Top row (shaded panels): Intra-site repeatability within the laboratory across three independent sessions (lab1, lab2, lab3). Bottom row (white panels): Comparison across scanning locations, where the laboratory data represents the mean of the three sessions. Tissue types include white matter (WM), gray matter (GM), and cerebrospinal fluid (CSF). Significant differences (Friedman test, $p < 0.05$) are indicated by asterisks (*).

Figure 9. Brain volumes in different tissue types measured from PDw (green), T2w (orange) and IR-T1w (blue) sequences. Top row (shaded panels): Intra-site repeatability within the laboratory across three independent sessions (lab1, lab2, lab3). Bottom row (white panels): Comparison across scanning locations (laboratory, ICU, and van), where the laboratory data represents the mean of the three sessions. No statistically significant differences were observed across locations for any tissue type or sequence ($p > 0.05$).

4. Discussion

LF MRIs are increasingly seen as potentially playing a pivotal role in democratizing MRI access in lower- and middle-income countries. They could also play a significant role in high-income countries, where such systems could be deployed in POC settings. However, as these systems are potentially more susceptible to environment-related fluctuations, a push to evaluate repeatability and reproducibility is essential. To address this, we assessed intra-subject repeatability (across different time points at the same location) and reproducibility (across three distinct environments) with our Halbach-based 47mT scanner. Quantitative SNR and CNR analyses across two brain regions, as well as volumetric tissue assessments, were performed on images acquired with three different MRI sequences (PDw, T2w, and IR-T1w). In agreement with MR physics(26), our results show that PDw scans yield the highest SNR. Those scans also exhibit the poorest CNR between WM and GM, as expected given the similar T_1/T_2 values of WM/GM at this field strength(27, 28). In contrast, T2w and IR-T1w scans offer the lowest SNR but the highest CNR. The IR-T1w scan offers an intermediate SNR scenario between the T1w and T2w scans, but no contrast between tissues and CSF.

Overall, the results show good intra-subject repeatability and reproducibility, with only minor environment-dependent variations observed in specific metrics, such as an increase in noise level in PDw scans in the van. While previous phantom studies using similar sequences at 50mT reported an SNR coefficient of variation (CoV) of approximately 6-7%(19), our in vivo SNR variability was slightly higher, ranging from 14% to 19% depending on tissue type and sequence. This increase is expected, as phantom studies benefit from optimal positioning at the bore center and a lack of motion or physiological noise. In vivo scans are constrained by subject anatomy (such as length of the neck) which can prevent perfect centering, and by the added complexity of segmenting heterogenous biological tissues compared with uniform phantom regions(29). Furthermore, although quantitative studies—such as T1 mapping at 64mT—have demonstrated higher reproducibility (~4%)(30), these methods are specifically optimized for quantitative studies. Our results therefore provide a realistic baseline for the stability of qualitative anatomical sequences across diverse, real-world imaging conditions.

Our volumetric findings for WM and GM (400–600 mL) are highly consistent with a previous report at 64 mT (31). Interestingly, while this study observed a significant overestimation of CSF volume (+24%) relative to their 3T benchmarks, our CSF volumes were in line with 3T values (see Table S5). This discrepancy between our and the 64 mT studies may be due to differences in coil coverage; while the system used in Ref.(31) uses a larger head coil with more extensive inferior coverage, our coil geometry ends approximately at the level of the nose. Although our volumetric values are more in line with the 3T results, the more limited brain coverage may exclude some inferior brain structures and CSF spaces from the total volume estimation, accounting for the lower absolute values.

While the present study focused on the reliability of single-orientation images without advanced post-processing, we recognize its growing role in this field. Studies have combined scans of orthogonal imaging directions into higher-resolution images(32) to improve accuracy in volume estimations (33), though others have found that such multi-scan approaches yield limited to no improvement in brain volume estimations respect to single-orientation scans(34). Recent literature also highlights the potential of image-to-image translation and synthetic contrast to bridge the gap between low- and high-field MRI. Tools such as LoHiResGAN(35) and SynthSR have shown impressive results in enhancing image quality and morphometric accuracy, particularly in clinical populations like those with Alzheimer’s disease(36). The integration of these super-resolution methods remains a promising avenue for future work, particularly for

sub-millimeter measurements like cortical thickness, where voxel size significantly impacts measurement precision(35).

A variety of other standard post-processing techniques could also be integrated into the pipeline. These include denoising algorithms, intensity inhomogeneity (bias field) correction, super-resolution, and correction for gradient nonlinearity. While such methods are expected to further improve quantitative metrics and visual quality, we intentionally performed our analysis on minimally processed, 'native' images. Our objective was to provide a foundational assessment of the scanner's inherent hardware performance, independent of the post-processing techniques of choice.

This study has several limitations that should be considered. Firstly, initial hardware constraints regarding coil geometry restricted participant recruitment. Two subjects were excluded at the beginning of the study because our 17-cm coil was too narrow to allow proper head positioning, resulting in insufficient brain coverage. To address this, a wider coil (width 20 cm) was recently built, which successfully allowed for imaging down to the level of the eyes when rescanning the previously excluded volunteers (see Supplementary S6). While this larger coil geometry resulted in a predictable reduction in SNR compared to the more compact design, due to the closer proximity of the coil to the shield, it significantly improved anatomical coverage and subject compatibility.

In one volunteer, brain coverage, though improved, remained suboptimal, stopping below the ventricle level, due to a shorter neck anatomy. This underscores a secondary constraint: the longitudinal length of the magnet, which causes the participant's shoulders to act as a physical barrier. In subjects with shorter necks, this 'shoulder limitation' prevents the head from reaching the magnet's isocenter. While transitioning to a shorter magnet design, as explored by other research groups(37) offers a potential solution for better head positioning, such a change involves a critical engineering trade-off. Future iterations must carefully balance magnet length to allow for isocentering the head while maintaining sufficient B0 homogeneity and minimizing gradient nonlinearity.

Secondly, the quantitative characterization of noise proved challenging. Noise estimation was performed using background regions in the image corners; however, this approach is susceptible to confounding factors such as residual signal from stimulated echoes and subtle reconstruction artifacts. While this is a common challenge in MRI, a more robust methodology, such as acquiring noise-only data (i.e. without RF excitation) could have provided a more precise noise floor for SNR and CNR calculations.

Finally, the statistical power of the study was limited by the small sample size ($n = 5$). While this cohort was sufficient for a feasibility study and qualitative overview, it precluded more granular statistical analysis. For example, although Friedman tests allowed us to account for the repeated-measures design, the minimum attainable p-value for post-hoc Wilcoxon signed-rank tests ($p = 0.0625$) exceeded conventional significance thresholds due to the mathematical constraints of the sample size. Consequently, these post-hoc results could not be formally interpreted, and future studies with larger cohorts are required to confirm the subtle differences between scanning environments and sequences.

Building on these initial results, several improvements for future research are identified. While this study was conducted on healthy volunteers to establish a baseline for repeatability and reproducibility, future work must focus on clinical translation. A critical next step involves evaluating the image quality and stability of VLF MRI in the ICU under more realistic conditions. While the current scans were performed in the ICU environment, they did not account for the EMI generated by active life-support equipment. Future investigations should perform phantom and volunteer scans while surrounded by operating ventilators, infusion pumps, ECG monitors, and pulse oximeters. Furthermore, the deployment of very low-

field MRI in Low- and Middle-Income Countries (LMICs) introduces unique challenges that extend beyond room-to-room portability. As highlighted in recent literature(38), infrastructural limitations such as frequent power outages can significantly impact image consistency. In these settings, achieving reproducible image quality even within a single location is a significant challenge. Future research should therefore investigate the feasibility of operating the scanner using low-cost, sustainable power sources, such as solar panels or dedicated battery-buffer systems. Critically, it will be essential to evaluate whether image quality and reproducibility are maintained when the system is powered solely by these alternative sources, which may introduce different noise profiles or voltage fluctuations compared to a stable hospital grid. Establishing that the scanner can provide consistent diagnostic information while running 'off-grid' would be a transformative step toward making bedside MRI a reality in the most remote and resource-constrained environments.

5. Conclusion

In this study, we evaluated the repeatability and reproducibility of our portable 47 mT Halbach scanner across three different locations. Although further investigations in larger and more clinically representative populations are required to confirm these findings under routine clinical conditions, our results establish an initial benchmark and highlight the importance of rigorous performance evaluation for portable low-field MRI. These efforts are critical to fully assess the potential of such systems and to facilitate their integration into clinical practice.

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6. References

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Supporting Information

Figure S1. Scan images from all volunteers, showing PDw (top) and T2w (bottom) contrasts acquired across five distinct scan sessions (Lab Sessions 1-3, ICU Session 1, Van Session 1). All images are from the same axial slice at the level of the ventricles.

Figure S2. Signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) measured from PDw, T2w and IR-T1w sequences, in white matter (WM), gray matter (GM), and cerebrospinal fluid (CSF), segmented by Synthseg, in Area 2 (ventricle level). Each data point represents the mean SNR from 5 slices, with different markers indicating the scan location. The boxplots summarize these data points for all locations, while colors differentiate individual subjects.

Figure S3. Contrast-to-noise ratio (CNR) from PDw, T2w and IR-T1w sequences, between different tissue types, as segmented by Synthseg, in Area 2 (ventricle level). The tissue types are white matter (“WM”), gray matter (“GM”), cerebrospinal fluid (“CSF”) and white and gray matter together (“Tissue”). The boxplots summarize these data points for all locations, while colors differentiate individual subjects.

Figure S4. Noise and signals in different tissue types measured from PDw (green), T2w (orange) and IR-T1w (blue) sequences in Area 2. Top row (shaded panels): Intra-site repeatability within the laboratory across three independent sessions (lab1, lab2, lab3). Bottom row (white panels): Comparison across scanning locations, where the laboratory data represents the mean of the three sessions. Tissue types include white matter (WM), gray matter (GM), and cerebrospinal fluid (CSF). Significant differences (Friedman test, $p < 0.05$) are indicated by asterisks (*).

WM volume (mL)	Ref.(31) at 64 mT	Ref.(31) at 3T	This study
Minimum	365.6	384.1	345.3
Maximum	597.5	622.8	550.9
GM volume (mL)	Ref.(31) at 64 mT	Ref.(31) at 3T	This study
Minimum	428.3	421.3	456.8
Maximum	641.5	659.6	629.0
CSF volume (mL)	Ref.(31) at 64 mT	Ref.(31) at 3T	This study
Minimum	237.1	168.5	173.7
Maximum	376.8	314.7	353.2

Table S5. Volumetric estimates of brain structures in the current study compared to literature. The table summarizes the minimum and maximum volume estimates (mL) for white matter (WM), gray matter (GM), and cerebrospinal fluid (CSF). Estimates from the current study (47 mT) are reported together with values from Ref. (31) obtained at 64 mT and high-field (3T) strengths.

Figure S6. Comparison of anatomical coverage between the standard and wider helmet coils. Representative images from two participants initially excluded due to head-width constraints. The orange square indicates for each volunteer the last identifiable slice with no/little artefacts using the standard coil and its corresponding slice with the larger coil. While the wider coil significantly improved anatomical inclusion for both subjects, coverage remained dependent on individual morphology. For Volunteer 2, the wider coil provided satisfactory longitudinal coverage. In contrast, for Volunteer 1, a shorter neck morphology acted as a physical barrier against the magnet, preventing the head from reaching the isocenter and resulting in suboptimal imaging of inferior brain structures